

Notas breves

A replacement name for *Calliostoma (Fautor) fernandesi* Boyer, 2006

Un nombre sustituto para *Calliostoma (Fautor) fernandesi* Boyer, 2006

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ABSTRACT

Calliostoma (Fautor) angolensis n. nov. is proposed as replacement name of *Calliostoma (Fautor) fernandesi* Boyer, 2006, junior homonym of *Calliostoma fernandesi* Rolán and Monteiro, 2006.

RESUMEN

Se propone *Calliostoma (Fautor) angolensis* n. nov. como nombre sustituto para *Calliostoma (Fautor) fernandesi* Boyer, 2006, homónimo posterior de *Calliostoma fernandesi* Rolán y Monteiro, 2006.

KEY WORDS: *Calliostoma*, homonymy, replacement name, Angola.

PALABRAS CLAVES: *Calliostoma*, homonimia, nombre sustituto, Angola.

Calliostoma (Fautor) fernandesi Boyer, 2006 was described as a new species from Angola in the December 2006 issue (24/2) of the Spanish malacological journal *Iberus* (BOYER, 2006). This issue of the journal was actually distributed on December 26th 2006 (pers. comm. of Emilio Rolán).

This species name must be considered as junior homonym of *Calliostoma fernandesi* Rolán and Monteiro, 2006, introduced for a new species from the Cape Verde Islands and published in the October 2006 issue (45/5) of the Belgian malacological journal *Gloria Maris*

(ROLÁN AND MONTEIRO, 2006). This issue of *Gloria Maris* was actually distributed on November 12th 2006 (pers. comm. of David Monsecour).

Both forms related to these names were compared and appear to be perfectly distinct from the point of view of their respective morphology and colour pattern. They are confirmed to belong to two different species, Rolán and Monteiro's species being endemic from deep water off the Cape Verde Archipelago, and Boyer's species being endemic from shallow water off central Angola.

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Accordingly to Art. 60 of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature, *Calliostoma* (*Fautor*) *angolensis* n.

nov. is proposed as replacement name of *Calliostoma* (*Fautor*) *fernandesi* Boyer, 2006.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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ROLÁN, E. AND MONTEIRO, A., 2006. A new *Calliostoma* (Mollusca, Calliostomatidae) from the Cape Verde Archipelago. *Gloria Maris*, 45 (5): 115-121.